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Preprint · December 2024

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21324.73608

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The Preparatory Drawing of “The Crucifixion of Saints Cosmas and Damian” by Michelangelo: Virtuosity in the Standardization of Anatomic Sketches

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Abstract

This article tells the story of one sketch by Michelangelo that at first glance seems almost sloppy and unimportant compared to his well-known and famous masterpieces. But an in-depth artistic anatomical examination discovers an extraordinary and almost one-off virtuosity, that will form the base of the anatomical art that will follow in its wake.

Keywords

Anatomy, Art, Michelangelo, The Crucifixion of Saints Cosmas and Damian

Introduction

Despite having cultivated a complex relationship over the years with Michelangelo, I must admit that I somehow managed to overlook the drawing whose praise I sing below. Perhaps this is due to the ancient but unfounded rumor, whose origins I have been unable to trace, to the effect that Michelangelo tended to “invent” muscles for his artistic needs. Perhaps I simply overlooked it, as my anatomical knowledge in the days when I was still a young artist was lacking, and to my shame, it simply passed me by. This is also a splendid opportunity to refute the common misperception regarding the artist’s anatomical inaccuracies and demonstrate that the opposite is true: Michelangelo’s level of precision is nothing short of extraordinary.

Painter, architect, and quintessential Renaissance man Michelangelo di Lodovico Buonarroti Simoni (1475–1564) was also an exceptional anatomist with a rare virtuoso ability to reduce his extensive knowledge of the human body to a few lines. An ink sketch he drew in 1517 serves as a test case. An almost arbitrary example of his multiple sketches, attesting to his trailblazing role in the relationship between the anatomical and artistic, and its application as a functional work tool at the highest standard that such a multidisciplinary relationship can offer.

I saw a copy of this drawing for the first time in *Michelangelo’s Universe (Le Carnets de dessins)*, a 1977 book by esteemed French author Gilles Lapouge.¹ Reproduced on page 85, the drawing’s permanent home is British Museum. It appears in several other places under different names, such as “Studies of Male Nudes,” or “Two Studies of a Crucified Man, One Tied to a Tree, the Other to a Cross-Beam.”

Michelangelo’s Milieu

Before I analyze this sketch, some background on Michelangelo’s artistic environment is in order. In the heyday of the Italian Renaissance, the anatomic discipline flourished, as did anatomical sketches, which became an essential artistic tool serving the aspiration of contemporary artists to produce accurate images, for which purpose they frequently dissected

¹ Journalist, essayist, critic and novelist, Gilles Lapouge is above all a prolific writer.

bodies and conducted anatomic studies of their own. Noteworthy in this regard is Michelangelo's senior and rival Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519), a prolific polymath in his own right, who performed no less than 20 dissections at the University of Pavia in 1510–11, together with anatomy professor Marcantonio della Tora.² Much has been written about Leonardo's sketches. Indeed, his attention to detail and understanding of human physiology were exceptional for his time; his dissection drawings remain among the finest ever created. Note, however, that Leonardo's anatomical writings and sketches were not printed during his time, but only between 1898 and 1916, meaning that he had very little actual impact on that science during the Renaissance. Nevertheless, the time invested by artists in studying the human body in his day not only improved their art but made them anatomic experts in their own right, with a daring and pioneering spirit that would eventually make artistic anatomy a key scientific tool in medical technologies.

This emerging relationship between medical science and anatomical art bore fruit with the publication of the seminal atlas of human anatomy, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica*.³ A collaboration between Flemish physician Andreas Vesalius—considered the founder of modern human anatomy—and Netherland-born Italian painter Jan Stephan van Calcar. The atlas represents one of the most revolutionary milestones in the history of the discipline of anatomy.⁴

Its predecessor was the ancient and flawed anatomic atlas by Greek physician Galen (Claudius Galenus), written in the second century CE.⁵ One reason for its multiple inaccuracies was the strict prohibition of dissections in the Roman Empire of his time. In view of the significant similarities between humans and Barbary apes, Galen dissected the latter and based his anatomical writings and sketches on them, which would serve as the authoritative basis for anatomy over the next 1300 years. Conversely, *De Humani Corporis Fabrica* provided accurate content and detailed sketches based on dissections of human bodies. Beyond being innovative and rich in unprecedented detail, van Calcar's etches are characterized by a modicum of morbid melodrama seasoned with Christian pathos that is typical of his time, reminding us that the bodies used for anatomic dissections were those of executed lawbreakers.

Returning to Michelangelo, he was not only a master painter and sculptor, but also a devoted anatomist who had already taken part in dissections by age 17. We are told of his major role in the history of anatomy by none other than Renaissance biographer Giorgio Vasari.⁶ Michelangelo collaborated with several anatomists and we have records of indirect contact between him and Vasilius. Vasari writes that Michelangelo was assigned a room where he regularly performed dissections at the hospital of the Santa Maria del Santo Spirito convent Florence, where he avoided drinking and eating for long durations. Vasari also wrote that

² Marco Antonio Della Torre and Leonardo da Vinci <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31050850/>

³ Vesalius, Andreas, 1514–1564 *De humani corporis fabrica* and *De fabrica* <https://collections.nlm.nih.gov/catalog/nlm:nlmuid-2295005R-bk>

⁴ Johannes Stephan van Calcar, (Giovanni de Calcar) 1499–1550 <https://www.artic.edu/artists/41653/jan-stephan-van-calcar>

⁵ Claudius Galen of Pergamum <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19816988/>

⁶ Giorgio Vasari *The Life of Michelangelo Buonarroti, Florentine Painter, Sculptor, and Architect* [1475–1564] <https://britishinstitutehoa.files.wordpress.com/2014/05/vasari-the-life-of-michelangelo.pdf>

Michelangelo's lifelong devotion to anatomical studies was absolute. Among other things, he sketched anatomical illustrations for an atlas by Realdo Colombo, Vesalius' bitter rival.⁷ For unknown reasons, some say due to financial disputes related to the printing of the atlas, Michelangelo destroyed all his drawings at the last minute, and only the text of the atlas was printed. In 1560, some four years before his death, he wrote: "who has not been, or is not a good master of the figure, and especially anatomy, cannot understand it."⁸

Analysis of the Drawing

In the preparatory drawing, which I call "Study for The Crucifixion of Saints Cosmas and Damian," for lack of a better name, Michelangelo offers us a quick and poignant simplification, as is his wont. Excessive confidence expressed by a uniform anatomic outline is exceptional even for a master such as Michelangelo. We can say that this is an almost error-free introduction to human anatomy. It is also a marvelous example of the artist's innovativeness: More than an indifferent, mechanistic anatomic specification, it is an opinionated expression. Michelangelo articulates in his graphic sketch a morbid intellect, concocting contours both mild and aggressive, and performing an alchemic act blending emotion and intellect. The result is a Renaissance piece of historic magnitude.

Executing a drawing as an ink sketch is difficult; there is no second chance and each doubling or repetition of a line testifies to hesitation. In contrast, each determined line attests to the artist's confidence and certainty. I will now analyze this drawing.

Figure A

The figure to the right of the crucified figure on the left side of the page, the figure's position is akin to something between dancing and leaning. In its lightness, it demonstrates exceptional virtuosity considering the relatively heavy mass of its mesomorphic body.

Nevertheless, despite its overall vitality, I would not be surprised if this posture was forced by the tradition of tying the cadaver to a tree, as in the atlas by Vesalius and van Calcar.

The left foot of the figure is stretched, and the tibialis muscle is almost completely replaced by and is barely visually distinct from the gastrocnemius muscle. Apparently, this blurring is designed to indicate a seemingly abnormal volume because of the pressure applied by the right leg to stabilize, pressuring the right knee, as attested by the spreading of the outstretched toes and maximal shrinking of the right gastrocnemius, creating a spherical structure.

Up the medial right leg, we note a separating line shaped like a diagonal S, elongated and vertical. Clearly, this is the sartorius, and its location is exquisitely precise. Similar to its formal characteristics—a short, sharp, and decisive line at the intersection of the fascia lata, left of the groin line emphasized by a diagonal line with repeated ink pressure—we gain the sense of additional tension in the position of the bent leg. At the same time, it enhances the presence of the Herculean oblique muscles, and from there we clearly perceive the tilt to the abdominal muscles—the rectus abdominis—almost static in their relative constriction in this position. The large right latissimus dorsi is impressively deployed, leaning on the branch

⁷ W. Bruce Fye, "Profiles in cardiology: Realdo Colombo"
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/clc.4960250311>

⁸ <https://www.thecollector.com/cadavers-to-learn-anatomy-renaissance-artists/>

behind. The left latissimus dorsi is hidden behind the biceps, half invisible and the other half appearing behind the same branch. The right hand and forearm are shortened toward the viewer, and the lines drawn on them depict their movement with a magnificent linear minimization. The right pectoralis major is also drawn with decisive touches in lines stretching toward the deltoid and is split into two to present a nontypical variation. The artist's choice to draw the diagonal lines of the sternum and clavicle with exquisite precision clarifies the position of the head even before they complete their dramatic journey to the right of the body. The trapezius muscles become elegantly rounded by the weight applied to them. On the left shoulder, we can spot a tiny nuance, a clavicular touch that could only find its way there thanks to the artist's minimization technique and a profound understanding of the limited axis of movement of the humerus in the direction of the scapula. The head and face are drawn with expressive lines based on a complete organic understanding of facial organs. Under the ear, a very short line indicating the movement of the sternomastoid can be seen. The mastoid process elegantly protrudes from the skull and the sternum is rendered with three confident lines.

Figure B: The Crucified

The figure's almost patchy beard is the most dominant of all the lines in the drawing, attesting to his importance and that of the drama of the position of the head. From there, a strong and determined line leading to the left shoulder further intensifies the tension. Unlike the figure to his right, the limbs almost disappear in deliberate neglect, suggesting the fatigue of the position. The rib cage and pectoralis become a single unit leaning to the right, where, like the rest, it tells the story of the sloped head. The legs, from the oblique lines and through the groin lines, depict a downward-sloping mass. The patella is clearly visible. The right leg rises somewhat at a shortened angle, which is evident in the shortened gluteus medius, and the lengths of the adductor and tibia are only hinted at. Conversely, the left leg is clearly visible, although the back of the leg is only hinted at with a light touch. Diagonal lines are thrown in to gradually fill in the figure from the right upward and from the left downwards.

The tree behind the figures is there to support them. The branches are coerced into providing specific support. Despite its talented composition, their role ends there.

Overview of the Drawing and Its Impact

As previously mentioned, the drawing is a quick and resolute ink sketch. This should not lead us to conclude that the sketching is in any way sloppy. Rather, it demonstrates exceptional anatomic drawing skills informed by a profound understanding of the human body, its volume, the strength of its muscles, and above all, its position and movements. Such an understanding can only be attained by deconstructing and reconstructing the body, rather than by drawing models through observation. This is indicated by the movements of the lines, because despite their expressiveness, they are under the artist's complete control. Their precise stopping points and angles reduce the volume from a complex anatomy to simple geometric organic shapes.

Note that the figures are slightly longer than those dictated by the Canon of Polykleitos, which was commonly used to determine bodily proportions in Michelangelo's time.⁹ Although the figures are generally based on Greco-Roman sculpture and the artist often refers to ancient artists as sources of inspiration, the sketch before us has innovative added value—primarily the reduction to simple lines that tell a complex anatomic and human story using a limited number of ink lines and spots.

This ink sketch, 16 × 24.9 cm, is a living testimony to the early standardization of genre anatomical drawing. Michelangelo's contemporaries and followers also produced detailed and in-depth anatomical sketches, but their abilities at linear minimization and constant de- and reconstructive movement from geometry to an essentially organic anatomy and back again were exceptional. The artist offers us a clean and intelligent figuration, a product that appears effortless but is actually the result of Sisyphean copying and meticulous learning—this is the secret of the simple magic we observe.

This expressive, opinionated, and minimalist approach to anatomic drawings may also be found in other Renaissance masters, such as Leonardo and Raphael. It is also found in the Flemish Baroque painter Peter Paul Rubens, who was directly affected by Michelangelo's work and even developed an anatomical methodology of his own, whose added value clearly suggests a geometric structure of organic anatomic relations and whose foundations were laid by Polykleitos and culminated in Michelangelo's sketches. This treasure of expressive anatomical tools is expressed in the works of artists who have observed the human body throughout history.

The daring and virtuosity in this exquisite blend of the anatomical and artistic that Michelangelo bequeathed to the world is found in almost every one of his works dealing with the human body, from the most immediate and straightforward sketch to the monumental "David." In this study, we find a raw display of skills that articulates this blend in an expressive and even abstract form until it becomes almost hidden from the naked, anatomically untrained eye.

This anatomical knowledge, combined with expressive skills, will only be found on rare occasions in the following centuries, sometimes in copying attempts of varying quality and often in attempts to emulate its flowing linearity and adopt the compound as a methodological approach to portrait painting and sculpting. A good example is the 1886 book *Drawing Course* by Jean-Léon Gérôme¹⁰ and Charles Bargue,¹¹ which offers a simple system that bridges the anatomical complexities and their linear simplification, and is used to this day as the "pocket Bible" of academic sketching.

Subsequently, in the 20th century, we encounter Michelangelo's standards and virtuosity in the form of a methodological discipline in the work of Gérôme's student, Canadian-born

⁹ Britannica biography of Polykleitos <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Polyclitus>

¹⁰ Jean-Léon Gérôme: French, Orientalist painter, draftsman and sculptor (born 5/11/1824 in Vesoul, Haute-Saône, Franche-Comté, France; died 5/1904 in Département de Ville de Paris, Ile-de-France, France).

¹¹ Charles Bargue Biography - Charles Bargue (1826–1883) was a French painter and lithographer, considered to be one of the most influential art teachers of the 19th century. <https://www.madridacademyofart.com/blog/charles-bargues-drawing-course>

draftsman and artistic anatomy scholar George Bridgman.¹² A trailblazing genius in his own right, he managed to bequeath Michelangelo's anatomical simplifications to many of his students, including Robert Beverly Hale¹³ and Andrew Loomis.¹⁴

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This standard of anatomical drawing that Michelangelo set in 1517, which used a minimal number of intensely expressive lines lives on, inspiring everyone appreciative of both science and art. His anatomical sketches are essentially different from those of other Renaissance masters. They are distinct from Raphael's softness and delicacy, as well as from the tight and simultaneously indistinct realism of Leonardo. They are also completely different from the works of modern and digital artists. There is nothing hesitant about Michelangelo's sketches: They are confident, primary, and even when they seem almost abstract scribbles, ultimately reveal themselves as a display of domesticated but wild choreography channeled onto the paper with a power relying on the art of giants such as Phidias¹⁵ or Polykleitos, and on the science of such geniuses as Herophilus¹⁶ and Galen, to sketch the mysteries of creation as captured by the form of the human body. With no words and only a few lines, Michelangelo di Lodovico Buonarroti Simoni sings the praise of humanity, uniting the primordial and modern in works that never cease to fascinate those with a passion for learning and beauty.

Author Contribution

The author confirms sole responsibility for the following: study conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results, and manuscript preparation.

¹² The Legacy of George B. Bridgman in the Work of His Students <https://asllinea.org/george-bridgman-drawing>

¹³ Dictionary of Art Historians Hale, Robert Beverly <https://arthistorians.info/haler>

¹⁴ Andrew Loomis Illustration History <https://www.illustrationhistory.org/artists/andrew-loomis>

¹⁵ Phidias Greek Sculptor <https://www.britannica.com/search?query=Phidias>

¹⁶ Herophilus Alexandrian physician <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Herophilus>

Michelangelo study for "crucifixion of saints cosmas and damian".

c.1517-1518 . ink 24.9 x 16 cm . British Museum, London.

Michelangelo study for "crucifixion of saints cosmas and damian".

Anatomical Drawing layer by Ziv Lenzner. Figure A & B.